

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ISLAMIC PREACHING (*DA'WAH*) AND SCIENTIFIC-POSITIVISTIC WORKS IN THE CONTEXT OF INDONESIAN STATE ISLAMIC UNIVERSITIES

Media Zainul Bahri

Department of Religious Studies,

Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University (UIN) of Jakarta

Abstract

This article elucidates two main points. First, the difference between *da'wah* (Islamic preaching) activities and scientific-positivistic works. *Da'wah*, for example, is a theological work. To preach is to invite/to call people to strengthen their beliefs and faith, do good, avoid bad deeds, and in many cases, preaching is to make judgments: right and wrong, misguidance or faith. Conversely, positivistic-scientific work is a scientific activity with methodological tools: there is empirical data (primary and secondary), there are approaches and theories, there are logical and rational explanations, and instead to strengthen belief and faith, scientific work is to find "scientific truth". There are ontological, epistemological and objective differences between *da'wah* activities and scientific-positivistic ways. Second, to this day there is still a big problem related to Indonesian State Islamic University (UIN) or Indonesian State Islamic Institute (IAIN): are these institutions a *da'wah* institution because there is an "Islam" within, or a scientific educational institution ones because it is also a university that demands a scientific-positivistic ways? This article uses historical, theological and philosophical approaches.

Keywords: Islamic preaching, Scientific-positivistic ways, Theological truth, Scientific truth, Indonesian State Islamic University (UIN) of Jakarta

Introduction

This article discusses something elementary but important about the difference between Islamic preaching (*da'wah*) activities and scientific-positivistic works, especially in the context of Indonesian Islamic Higher Education such as UIN (Universitas Islam Negeri, State Islamic University) and IAIN (Institut Agama Islam Negeri, State Islamic Institute). A sort of a "common words" or meeting point, or separation points between *da'wah* and scientific works with its methodological tools. Many Muslims or religious people have the view that there is a "close relationship" between *da'wah* and scientific works, and some of them even assert that *da'wah* activity is a scientific work because "the content of *da'wah* is science" and preaching also "conveys science". However, some questions could arise: "what is science", "what kind of science?", and how to "treat that science?" I would like to discuss these problems. As for me, the character of both is different as the way of working and the paradigm of the two are also different.

Understanding the Character of Islamic Preaching (*Da'wah*)

Da'wah, an Arabic word and becomes an Islamic term, is very closely connected to with. The area of *da'wah* is indeed the territory of "faith". First, people preaching means campaigning for their "faith, religion, beliefs, and religious ideology" to others. Second, people who preach "invite others" to follow the religious beliefs of the preacher. Third, people preaching means, usually, campaigning that other people's religious beliefs, understandings and their religious practices are wrong, false and heretical. Then the preacher shows that his religious beliefs and practices are correct, or the most correct, or shows that "his understanding and sect" is correct. But other's understanding and the sect are wrong. Fourth, in a general sense, preaching means

"inviting people" to do good or good things, and inviting people not to do bad things. What is considered of good and bad things usually based on religion or general norms/culture that are considered established.

In Islam, generally (although there are special cases), Islamic studies are closely related to *da'wah*. That is, the objectives of the Islamic studies are (1) to strengthen faith, (2) as a tool to understand the Quran, Sunnah (prophet tradition) and the views of the Islamic scholars (*Ulema*), (3) to show what is good and what is wrong, (4) to show which ones should be followed and which ones should be avoided: halal food and drinks, for example, and not halal ones. (5) to show practices that draw closer to God and shows actions that keep away from God.

The science of *Kalam* (Islamic theology), for example, is a science that is used for "the benefit of *da'wah*". The primary subjects in the science of *kalam* are the arguments of *naqli* (the Quran, hadith, and views of *Ulema*) to be used as "guidelines for understanding and practicing religion". Rational arguments (in Arabic, '*aqli*') are used to strengthen the *naqli* argument. Generally, it is like that. Although there are special cases which *Kalam's* Islamic Scholar (*Ulema*) does not use *naqli* arguments at all. Entirely he uses the argument of reason ('*aqli*'). If that's the case, usually he is no longer referred to as a scholar of *Kalam* (a theolog), but he is a philosopher. So, the basis of *Kalam Science* is "faith". Reason arguments are used to "strengthen faith (*naqli*)". For this reason, in the *Kalam Science* of the classical period, the *Kalam's* Islamic scholars disbelieved one another and considered themselves the most righteous (1). Look at the Sunni people as well as Muktazili, Qadari, Jabari, Murji'i, Shi'ite, Khawarij, al-Ghazali, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Taymiyyah, and many others. They disbelieve and mislead one another. It turns out that today on Youtubes it is easy for us to

see the Islamic preachers of different sects are fighting one with each other's.

Thus, *first*, the base of *da'wah* is "faith"; the material or subject of preaching is religion (Islam) and culture (preaching of any culture). If drawn more broadly, the subject could also be "ideology": people preaching ideology, ideology they believe in, any ideology. But in this paper, we only focus on "religious preaching" not an ideology. If we examine, then *second*, the character of *da'wah* is campaigning religious doctrines or inviting people to follow the religious doctrines of the preacher. There are various models of *da'wah* and various ways so that *da'wah* can be effective. *Third*, the source of *da'wah* is revelation or the words of God and the words of the Prophet: an authority beyond humans. Reason and argument are used in preaching to strengthen the authority of revelation and the authority of the words of the Prophet. While the purpose of *da'wah* is to build a "religious society" as desired by God as a figure who becomes "the centre of religion" or the centre of religious people. So, from upstream to downstream, *da'wah* activities are theological work. What I mean by *da'wah* work in this article is in form of "oral speech" and "writing" (books or articles) which are indeed conducted for the purpose and benefit of *da'wah*.

In science or scientific activities, which are commonly used in Islamic higher education, there are several approaches to understanding Islam: sociological, anthropological, psychological, theological, phenomenological, philosophical, political and others (2). Generally in preaching (*da'wah*) that is commonly used is a "theological approach", only one approach. In preaching Islam, ustadz or Ulama uses arguments: verses of the Qur'an or Hadith which are then explained in detail through the opinions of classical and modern Ulema: Tafsir (Quranic exegesis), Hadith (prophet's sayings), Fiqh (Islamic law), Islamic history and so on. Generally, in *da'wah* work, only theological approach. As great as Gus (son of Kyai in Java), Kyai (Indonesian Islamic figure), or Ulema are in preaching, usually using theological material. His approach is also theological. It is almost rare or even we never hear that preaching speeches or writings using theories strictly in social sciences or modern philosophy other than theological. In fact, Islamic scientific studies or Islamic studies cover something broader than just theological material and theological approaches (3).

What is a Scientific-Positivistic Character? How They Work?

In Arabic, the word "*ilmiyyah*" being "scientific" in English and Indonesian, means "scientifically", or "there is knowledge/science over there", or "closely related to science or knowledge". A science if separated, comes from knowledge. There are also many scientists who combine to be "science of knowledge": there are science and knowledge at the same time. Knowledge, said Philosophers, means facts, actual, or factual conditions that we obtain through observation, experience and association. Professor Jujun Suriasumantri said, knowledge, basically, is anything we know about everything, about anything, from the simplest to the most complex (4, 193). While "science" is a collection of

knowledge that compiled or abstracted systematically by following the standards of the scientist/scientific community. In the Philosophy of Science (5) for example, new knowledge can be called science if it follows the conditions: it must have ontological, epistemological and axiological aspects: Science must be able to explain "what", "how", "where", "why" and "what for". Some say every science must contain knowledge. There is also a scholar who say that science is a branch of knowledge. I have no interest in joining the debate. From the combination of science and knowledge, or vice versa: knowledge and science, "scientific knowledge" is born. I will use the positivistic standard of modern scientific knowledge that was born in Western Europe, whether during the Age of Reason (6) or the Age of Adventure (7), or the Age of Analysis (8), or whatever you call it. This modern-scientific knowledge currently used as a standard of scientific study in all higher education institutions on this planet.

The *basic* characteristics of scientific knowledge is empirical. In "scientific work" the data is available, both factual and empirical, and visible. The object is empirical data. "Scientific work" in the context of modern scientific knowledge must have "primary and secondary data" which we then call "references". Data or references must be empirical, cannot be supernatural or invisible. That is not possible. Are there students and lecturers at IAIN and UIN who write scientific papers: Essay, Thesis and Dissertation without empirical primary and secondary data? That should be impossible. Nothing is non-empirical. Scientific work that does not have primary data and empirical secondary data, I guarantee it will not be scientific work.

The *subject* of scientific-positivistic works is "human beings" or "human experience" with all its limitations. Our knowledge about reality, about anything, or about the object of study, which is then processed by reason, is the subject of scientific work. Observation and reading of reality, data, by mobilizing our rational and reasoning abilities, will later become 'a school of Rationalism'. Reading and observing empirical data by directing our sensory abilities, later became 'a school of Empiricism'. Rationalism and Empiricism are major schools to find scientific truth, which is actually "the working method of reason and experience" in positivistic scientific work. More recently there have been attempts to blend Rationalism and Empiricism (9).

In religion, as being told, "intuition" and "revelation" must be added. Both are considered as a source of science and knowledge. But in positivistic-scientific work what is called intuition and revelation that can be used as scientific work is what has been written into text or in the form of text. The views of Sufism of al-Ghazali, Ibn Arabi, al-Qushairi and others, which they previously obtained through intuition (*kashaf*), which have now been written into "classical books" are the objects of scientific work. The text is existed. The goods are existed. Not something unseen. Likewise, what is referred to as revelation and Hadith, has now become the holy book of the written Quran and written books of Hadith. In other words, we study "the written text of Sufism" as well as "the written text of the Quran and Hadith". Obviously, the data is empirical. In the

light of scientific-positivistic work that the Prophet received revelations from God or the Prophet recited Hadiths guided by God, cannot be verified. How to verify something unseen, which is invisible? Only the faith of believers that who believe that it is true that the Prophet received revelations from God. Belief is not an empirical and in its territory is faith. What can be studied scientifically now is the holy book of the Quran and books of Hadith which already become "written texts". In *da'wah* work, the holy books (the Quran), the traditions of the Prophet (Hadith or Sunna) and the writings of the Ulema are indeed read and researched/studied but, once again, to be preached with the interest of "strengthening faith", not to seek or to find the scientific truth.

We may call the scientific-positivistic way of working as a "methodological device". *First*, there must be a Study Approach. In Islamic/Religious scientific studies there are many approaches: theological, historical, philosophical, phenomenological, sociological, anthropological, psychological, political and others, each of which actually originates from the subject of the course: theology [Kalam, Tafsir (Quranic exegesis), Hadith (prophet's sayings), Fiqh (Islamic law), etc.], history of religion, philosophy of religion, phenomenology of religion, sociology of religion, anthropology of religion, psychology of religion and so on. To approach, in a research work, means "the way we explain". *Second*, there must be a theory. We have to describe the primary and secondary data that we have with one or two or three approaches above, but what theory do you want to read or to analyse the data? For example, there is a good dissertation (a doctoral thesis) on the Islamization of the Archipelago of Indonesia, which read by "Foucault's Theory" of Episteme and Power Relations. Indonesian Muslim scholars have already know how this archipelago was Islamized, but the "Foucauldian reading model" of Power Relations shows that the archipelago was Islamized with "intellectual power", "cultural power" and "political power", that is an interesting study, and in some ways, it is the "new reading" way. The author of the dissertation, an academic at UIN Raden Mas Said Surakarta, proposed a "new theory" which he called the *Teori Episteme Islamisasi* (Episteme theory of Islamization) which complements established theories about the Islamization of the Archipelago (10). There are also many scientific works in religious studies/Islamic studies that examine "Religious Texts" by dismantling them through several theories in Critical Discourse Analysis.

In the Study of Religions, for example, people want to study Religion. There are several subjects. *First*, The Essence of Religion: what is the Essence of Religion? There are 25 paradigms and theories in it (from classical to modern). *Second*, The Origin of Religion: where did the origins of religion come from? There are 20 theories in it (from classical to modern). *Third*, The Phenomenon of Religion or the Phenomenology of religion: what lies behind the appearance of all religious activities? There are 15 theories in it (from classical to modern). *Fourth*, The Function of Religion: there are 25 theories in it (from classical to modern). *Fifth*, The Language of Religion: there are 20 theories

in it (from classical to modern). *Sixth*, The Comparison of Religions, there are 25 theories in it (from classical to modern) (11), and so on. *Third*, an exploration (12). In scientific-positivistic work, we will be invited to have an adventure to explore the subject. There are countless examples of exploration, it can be deep (intensive), or it can be broad (extensive), in many disciplines of the social sciences, humanities or natural sciences. I would like to cite an example in the History of Religion as written by Karen Armstrong. Armstrong wrote a thick book with such an exploratory works. Through her books *History of God* (Indonesian edition 580 pages) (13) and *The Great Transformation* (Indonesian edition 510 pages) (14), Armstrong explores the history of religious people's conception of God since thousands of years ago and how religion not only faces changing times but also continues to transform with the times. Through *The Holy War* (Crusades, Indonesian edition 920 pages), *Fighting for God* (Indonesian edition 640 pages) (15), and *Fields of Blood, the History of the Relationship of Religion and Violence* (Indonesian edition 692 pages) (16), Armstrong diligently explored the "character" and "paradigm" of religion which led her to the findings of the study that "religion never actually erupts or shouts war". There are many non-religious factors. It is wrong, said Armstrong, if many scholars regard religion as the source of war and disaster. Through *The Lost Art of Scripture, Rescuing the Sacred Texts* (2019) (17), Armstrong traced religious texts carefully which led her to the conclusion that the "basic traits" of religion are right-brain: love, art, spirituality, empathy and morals. The character of religion is love and peace. But some religious people prefer to understand religion with the left brain: logical and rational which results in a religious view that religion is rigid, dry, dogmatic, black and white.

In the study of Southeast Asia, examples of highly explorative scientific works can be presented. Professor Azyumardi Azra's scientific work on the *The Origin of Islamic Reformism In Souteast Asia, Networks of Malay-Indonesia and Middle Eastern Ulama in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries* (18), not only explorative and admirable, but also unmatched until now. There is also Sartono Kartidirdjo's work on the *Banten Peasant Revolt in 1888* (19); Kuntowijoyo's work on *History of Social Change in Madurese Agrarian People of 1850-1940* (20); three volumes of *Nusa Jawa Silang Budaya* by Denys Lombard (21); three volumes of *Islamisation of Java from the 14th century to the early 21st century* by Ricklefs (22); and three volumes *Kuasa Ramalan Pangeran Diponegoro* by Peter Carey (23). The names above: Azyumardi, Sartono, Kuntowijoyo, Ricklefs, Denys Lombard and Peter Carey, are works of "*babad alas*" or "opening the wilderness" of science and knowledge. They make a mapping and give us information which are the centre, which are the edges, which are the big trees, which are the small trees. They provide knowledge about the history and thinking constructs (*Epistème*) of a society at a certain time. They dismantle the *Epistème* and the spirit of a society or nation, connect it with other peoples and nations, looking for patterns that are the same and different so they can find: what is actually "constant" in human history, and

what is “constantly changing”. In this exploratory-scientific work, they read and study with diligence and discipline: primary and secondary sources, manuscripts and various other texts, government records from top to bottom, notes of travellers, notes of writers: romances, novels, short stories and folklore written at that time, and others. With extraordinary energy and persistence, they summarize, process, classify and relate the various records (data) to one another. Are there *da'wah* works (or *da'wah* books) in the modern era with a broad and deep level of exploration like their works?

Fourth, fifth and sixth are coherent, consistent in using data, approaches, theories and arguments, and systematic. The mindset and method of scientific work are systematic in nature, meaning that they are continuous, do not jump around and do not produce various thoughts and jumping conclusions, as well as coherence: there is a connection or integration between one aspect and other aspects. Positivistic scientific work is only loyal to data, namely data about the reality of the object being studied. As already mentioned, the data must be empirical, not something supernatural or invisible. The data is processed with “methodological tools” as explained above. For this reason, the sole objective of scientific work is to find the “truth of science” or “true object reality” or “which is closer to the truth” of facts and reality. From this, one can see the main difference between *da'wah* work aimed at “strengthening faith” and scientific-positivistic work aimed at discovering “the truth of reality/object”, whether that reality is normative-textual or a sociological-empirical real phenomenon. The most important thing is to find the truth of reality.

On the final ascent of scientific work is identifying “novelty, discovery, inventions or innovations”. In natural sciences, for example, discovery is finding something unexpected during research and such discovery is not yet existed in the body of knowledge. Meanwhile, an invention is something that has not existed before which is made from existing raw materials. While innovation is “change” to increase the “added value” of something that exists (24, p. 325-326). In the field of social sciences and humanities, including religious studies, the term “novelty” or “study findings” which is then abstracted into “new thesis” are terms similar to inventions and innovations in the natural sciences. In all scientific works of Islamic studies, ideally, there should not only be “study findings” but also “novelties”: novelty in new references, new methodologies, new theses and new theories, or “new readings” about the object of study; new in the sense that it has not been discovered or has not been used by other scholars in a similar field of science. Or at least what is called as a new is “reinforcing old theories/thesis with new evidence” or is “rejecting old theories/thesis with new evidence”, is or “really discovering new ones”.

After this positivistic scientific work has been completed, the last stage is to be tested or to be examined; to be tested at “legality, validity, and consistency” in using methodological tools by the scientific community in accordance with the scientific field/area. Thus, attitudes such as critical (constantly questioning the reality and validity of data or references), exploratory

(diving in depth and breadth), consistent in using methodological tools, and novelty or new readings or new thesis, are the hallmarks of scientific work. which may be slightly or much different from the attitude and mindset that exists in *da'wah* work.

The positivistic-scientific works for centuries, both the processes and the products they produce, are amazing. Not only sharp, careful and observant in reading the reality of the physical world, scientific work has also enriched life, provided medicine and empirical certainty (in natural sciences), provided solutions, offered alternative paths and finally pushed the horizons of science, art, knowledge, religion and humanity as long as far the exploration of human capabilities and experience up to their limits. From the basic character, method of work and purpose of both (preaching work and scientific work) we find that there are some fundamental differences. Both have different subject worlds and areas, in several key ways. Although later we will see that there are common words and intersection points.

What about State Islamic Universities (UIN and IAIN), and Private Islamic Universities/Institutes?

In fact, all universities, institutes, higher education or colleges are the same, whether they are religion-based or public universities. In Indonesia, even throughout the world, academic work or scientific work is practically the same: both are positivistic. At UIN or IAIN all scientific-academic activities have the same basis: (1) there must be empirical data; (2) there must be an approach and theory. There are dozens of approaches: theological, historical, philosophical, phenomenological, philological, sociological, anthropological, psychological, political and others. There are dozens of theories along with the approaches; (3) exploratory; and (4) critical; (5) study findings, novelty and what is the new thesis. If numbers 6 and 7 are added, the “construction/mindset” of scientific work is “consistent, coherent and systematic”, in other words; not jumping around so as not to produce “a jumping conclusions”. This is the first character of the University.

All Muslim scholars, in the context of Islamic scientific studies, agree that Islam has two aspects: normative Islam and historical Islam or practiced Islam or living Islam. Normative Islam is Islam as it is written in “texts”: the text of the Quran, Hadith, or the writings of the Islamic scholars (Ulema). So usually the approaches used are: theological, historical, philological, hermeneutic, and philosophical (textual studies). Meanwhile, historical Islam or living Islam usually uses sociological, anthropological, psychological, political and phenomenological approaches: studying socio-anthropological of how Muslims practice Islam. Academic books entitled “Islam in Java”, or “Islam in Sundanese People”, or “Islam among Bourgeoisie people” or “Islam in West-Borneo”, or “Islam in South Sulawesi”, or “Indonesian Sufis in West-Java” and so on are usually sociological, anthropological, psychological, and phenomenological studies/approaches. Every-

thing: the subject, object, reference, and data are empirical. This is what I mean by positivistic: Counted, Talled, Numbered, and Measured.

The second character of the University is “an academic freedom” or “freedom of opinion”, based on academic data that has been processed with methodological devices as described above. All academics at the University who have an “academic database” or “scientific-positivistic work” then have a freedom to have “an opinion”, to “speak out” or to “make conclusions” which should not be hindered by anyone and any authority, unless it can be refuted, rejected, and debated only by the “academic community”, or “other academic opinions” whose basis is the same as academic database. In its history, the university which came from the Latin “*universitas magistrorum et scholarium*” in the years around 1155-1158 had an academic document entitled “*Constitutio Habita*” that in it found a dictate about “freedom right of academic”, which was then upheld by all universities around the world.

In the context of “Islamic studies” which is closely related to the University paradigm above, through the first and second characteristics: empirical data, critical, exploratory, can be explained logically and rationally and can be verified (tested), recently problems have emerged in the academic world of Islamic college. First and foremost, in the spirit of scientific-positivistic work, all realities or all data objects of study are treated as data, not as “sacred texts” neither as “taboo objects”. Muslim scholars respect the Quran, Hadith, or the writings of the Islamic scholars because they have faith. This territory is faith. But as research study data, these texts are treated as profane research data, not the sacred ones. However, the problem arises, since long ago, the positivistic standard of Islamic scientific studies was “criticized” or “judged” by Islamic faith (*Sharia*). The case of Nasr Hamid Abu Zayd is a factual example. Abu Zayd is an academic, linguistic expert, who is excellent, and critical in Quranic studies. As a positivistic scholar of Linguistics, Abu Zayd undertook highly critical readings of the texts of the Quran and the writings of Imam Shafi’i (25). As an academic, he fully follows the “modern academic standard”: critical, explorative, logical, consistent and systematic. But unfortunately, Abu Zayd’s readings were judged by the Sunni faith of the professors at Cairo University, Egypt. The rejection of Abu Zayd to be full professor was supported by many al-Azhar scholars and professors. The results of Zayd’s studies are considered to deviate from Sharia, especially Sunni Sharia. His Professorship’s application was rejected. The Egypt religious court sentenced him as an apostate. Cases like Nasr Abu Zayd are common in Muslim countries. Not a few Muslim scholars who are critical in Islamic studies have experienced to be humiliated because they are considered to have committed blasphemy against Islam.

Theologians and preachers, generally (though not all) are emotional people. Since the time of classical theology: Sunni, Muktazili, Qadari, Jabari, and Shi’ite as I mentioned above, until now, they like to conflict and to mislead one with each other. Meanwhile, positivistic-scientific work, in its basic nature, is work that

is calm, diligent, thorough, careful, unhurried, unemotional, and generally “lonely-alone”. To produce some quality works, Humanists or Social scientists must concerned diligently for years. Likewise, scientists must be “imprisoned” in laboratories for years looking for formulas according to the subject and object of their research.

The second problem is that there are a lot of academic works at UIN/IAIN that contain more “*da’wah*” or do not meet the scientific-positivistic standards. There are not a few theses, lecturer articles/books, and especially journal articles in the era when journals are booming nowadays, which are actually more filled with propaganda, not serious academic debate. People wrote the classical Muslim scholars such as al-Ghazali, Ibn Arabi, Ibn Taymiyah, Ibn Sina, Ibn Rushd and others whose contents were very descriptive, and usually preaching Islam or preaching their thoughts, but there was no critical study and no “new thesis” about them. In the Middle Ages, those scholars were the inventors of “knowledge” and “methodology” as well. They were, in their time, innovators, inventors, and creators of new theses. Scholars such as Ghazali, Ibn Arabi, Ibn Taymiyah who wrote themes on Theology and Sufism for dozens of volumes, as well as Tafsir experts such as At-Tabari (also as historian), Zamakhshari, and Fakhrudin Razi, are scientists who work encyclopaedically, critically and highly explorative. There is Ibn Sina who wrote volumes on theology, logic and medicine. There is Ibn Khaldun who conducts “historical, sociological, and anthropological” studies of Arab society. There is Imam Ash’ari who wrote theological-descriptive-analytical writings, *Maqalat Islamiyyin*, several volumes. There is Al-Biruni who lived in India for two years then made a historical, theological and anthropological description of Hindu-Indian society through his work *Tahqiq Ma Lil Hindi*. Their works are volumes. There is also the historian Al-Baladzuri who wrote volumes of *Futuhul Buldan* (the Origins of the Islamic State), and many more.

Now, in my opinion, there are things that are still relevant from their works such as historical reviews, spirituality and a set of Islamic moral/ethical guidelines. But the most important thing is the “renewal of interpretation”, “recontextualization” and “re-actualization” of their works, because now times have changed, the problems they face are more complicated and sophisticated. Abdurrahman Wahid or Gus Dur (1940-2009), as the most prominent traditionalist and neo-modernist figure in Indonesia, since the 1990s has challenged Indonesian Muslims to carry out “new readings” or “new thesis” of the classic works above and to formulate “new methodologies”, not only to follow blindly to these above Islamic scholar works (26, p. 25).

Indonesian Muslim Scholars Preaching? What Kind of Preaching?

State Islamic University (UIN) of Jakarta was originally named ADIA: Akademi Dinas Ilmu Agama (was established in 1957). From its name it has been obvious: higher school for candidates of bureaucrats or service officials at Islamic institutions. In the 1960s ADIA changed to *Al-Jamiah al-Islamiyyah* in the sense of IAIN. When the G 30S PKI (Indonesian communists

movement) incident erupted in 1965 to 1967, IAIN concentrated on developing Islamic *da'wah* vis a vis (confronting) the PKI movement which always belittled religion. A lot of energy is focused on *da'wah*. From the late 1950s to the early 1990s, IAIN had almost become an Islamic higher education institution with the main missions of "Islamic *da'wah*" and the "development of Muslim communities". It was only in the early or mid-1990s that critical figures and academics, especially alumni from the West, developed various scientific-positivistic approaches to Islamic studies. If traced chronologically, the literacy tradition of IAIN has only started seriously since the mid-1980s. Literacy tradition means: (1) reading books or references that are correct; (2) after reading the correct references, then reading critically; (3) have a writing tradition; (4) write critically. The tradition of reading and writing correctly and critically can be said to have started from the 1990s to the 2000s. The year 2000 marked the beginning of the emergence, slowly but massively, of journals with articles in English, and since the 2010s a tradition of critical writing emerged (massively at UIN and IAIN) in international journals, which has continued to this day. Because of this, the "literacy" traditions of IAIN and UIN are not old and not strong, when compared to another large universities in Indonesia.

It was in the context of the development of Islamic *da'wah* and Muslim society from the late 1950s to the late 2000s that IAIN figures and scholars emerged who were actively involved in developing *da'wah*. Popular figures names like Harun Nasution developed rational Islamic *da'wah* by following Muktazili school; Nurcholish Madjid preaches modern Islam and civilizational Islam; Gus Dur preached cosmopolitan Islam and Indonesian indigenous Islam; Amin Rais preached modern Islam and social monotheism; Syafi'i Ma'arif preaches modern Islam; Kuntowijoyo preached the objectification of Islam and Islamic scholarship; Jalaluddin Rakhmat preached a Sufistic Islam of the Shi'ite model; Komaruddin Hidayat preaches modern and contextual Islam. Also there are Azyumardi Azra, Dawam Rahardjo, Djohan Effendi, Moeslim Abdurrahman campaigning for progressive and transformative Islam, and many other figures, especially the generations after them. The figures and academics above are scholars who almost all have scientific-positivistic works in the field of Islamic studies or social sciences because most of them studied in Western universities or were influenced by positivistic Western scientific models.

They were fully aware that at that time (1970s to 2000s), some Indonesian Muslims were in an era of transition from traditional to modern culture or some others were living in a modern and post-modern culture that needed "Islamic moral guidelines". The Muslim figures above, who are actually scholars, in the sense of having a modern-positivistic scientific basis, must be involved and participate in formulating the development of Muslim society. In this context, they also have to actively preach. However, because they are Muslim scholars who have now become modern scholars, their *da'wah* model feels and looks high, a kind of "high *da'wah*", also because the objects of their *da'wah* are

mostly educated middle-class urban Muslims. They are "Muslim thinkers", in the sense that they think hard about models of Islamic thought/understanding that are compatible with the culture of society and the world which is constantly changing and stretching. May we call them "scholars cum activists" or "scholars cum preachers".

If UIN and IAIN cannot or are unable to give up *da'wah* work because they have the letter "I" (Islam) in them, then there are five (5) alternatives that can be practiced: (1) continue to develop scientific-positivistic works but all scientific works are used for the benefit of *da'wah*. Because of this, scientific works have been limited or "selective": only those that can be used for *da'wah* purposes are selected; (2) more focused on scientific works only. The focus of *da'wah* work is only about 30 percent; (3) more focused on *da'wah* works. The focus of scientific work is only 30 percent; (4) fifty-fifty: Some focus on *da'wah* work, some focus on scientific work; (5) fully focusing on Islamic scientific studies with scientific-positivistic work tools. *Da'wah* aspects are the implications and consequences of scientific work. Choosing any of the five alternatives above must be prepared with quite serious consequences. If you still have to preach, maybe UIN and IAIN have priorities. Large UINs with great figures preach Islam, science and humanity at the world level: think about and offer solutions to global issues. However, there are UIN and IAIN which are more focused on the local "Muslim community", unable to think about regional and global problems. What I call 'able' or 'unable' means it depends on the vision and mission, funding capability, and priorities of each UIN and IAIN.

Conclusion

With all of the above explanations, it is clear that there are fundamentally significant differences between *da'wah* work and scientific-positivistic work. Paradigm, *Epistème*, ways of working and goals are different, although there is a meeting point between them. Nevertheless, one thing must be acknowledged, not only human culture, but today's world civilization, is heavily coloured by *da'wah* works from world religions and scientific works, in addition to other factors such as political and economic constellations. Both are different but cannot be ignored. Because of that, one cannot rashly call one superior to the other. The truth is: both of them have "different worlds". Both of them exist in different 'two rooms', and can greet each other when they leave each other's rooms. There are many people, from various segments, who like to be preached. There are also many educated people who are not happy with *da'wah* but prefer to read scientific works and Islamic scientific studies. There are religious people who return to get "refreshment of faith" because of being preached. There are also people who feel it is "a waste of time" to listen to preaching which they consider only campaigning for 'conservatism' and 'backwardness'. This last group feels that they have found God and a 'new faith' because they are amazed by the positivistic scientific products, not because of preaching.

However, what Indonesian Muslims have to campaign for is a habit of knowledge; loves the nature of

science, especially in its critical aspect: that Muslims must be critical, get used to thinking and being critical, logical, rational, and have an explorative spirit: discovering something new. The rites and spirituality that Muslims diligently follow in no way prevent them from having the basic scientific mindset and character as above. Finally, even if they have to preach; knowledge science is used for *da'wah*, then *da'wah* is to develop human values that have dignity, for justice and human equality, and *da'wah* is to save humanity and this earth from global destruction.

References

1. In the Middle Ages, this can be read, for example, from the works of Abdul Qahir bin Thahir bin Muhammad al-Baghdadi, Al-Farqu Baynal Firaq; see also Abdul Karim Shahrastani, Al-Milal wa Nihal; it can also be read from several parts of Al-Ghazali's writings (not all of them); it can also be read in many passages from the writings of Ibn Taymiyyah and many theological works of scholars of the period. Whereas in modern times the writings of Indonesian writers who attack each other, mislead and disbelieve different Islamic understandings can be read, for example, Tim Penulis MUI Pusat, Mengenal & Mewaspadai Penyimpangan Syiah di Indonesia (2013); Mamduh Farhan Buhairi, Syiah, Kesesatan di atas Kesesatan (2013); Ahmad Lutfi Fathullah, Menguak Kesesatan Aliran Ahmadiyah (2005); M. Amin Djamaluddin, Ahmadiyah & Pembajakan Al-Qur'an (2005); M. Amin Djamaluddin, Ahmadiyah Menodai Islam (2007); M. Amin Djamaluddin, Kupas Tuntas Kesesatan & Kebohongan LDII: Lembaga Dakwah Islam Indonesia (2008); M. Amin Djamaluddin, Bahaya Islam Jamaah LDII Lemkari (2013); Badruddin H. Subky, Bid'ah-Bid'ah di Indonesia (1993); Abduh Tuasikal, Mengenal Bid'ah Lebih Dekat (2017); Mahrus Ali, Bongkar Kesesatan, Debat Terbuka Kyai NU (2010); Mahrus Ali, Mantan Kyai NU Menggugat Shalawat dan Dzikir Syirik (2007); Mahrus Ali, Membongkar Kesesatan Kyai-Kyai Pembela Bid'ah Hasanah, Sudah Jelas Bid'ah itu Sesat Kok Masih Saja Dianggap Baik (2007); Abdul Hakim bin Amir Abdat, Risalah Bid'ah (2001); Hartono Ahmad Jaiz, Aliran dan Paham Sesat di Indonesia (2002); Hartono Ahmad Jaiz, Mengungkap Kebatilan Kyai Liberal CS (2010); Hartono Ahmad Jaiz, Bahaya Islam Liberal (2002); Hartono Ahmad Jaiz, Menangkal Bahaya JIL dan FLA (2004); and much more.

2. For these approaches see Peter Connolly, ed. (1999). *Approaches to the Study of Religion*.

3. For approaches to Islamic studies see for example M. Amin Abdullah. (2012). *Islamic Studies di Perguruan Tinggi, Pendekatan Integratif-Interkoneksi*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar. M. Amin Abdullah. (2020). *Multidisiplin, Interdisiplin dan Transdisiplin, Metode Studi Agama & Studi Islam di Era Kontemporer*. Yogyakarta: IB Pustaka. Azim Nanji, ed. (2015). *Peta Studi Islam, Orientalisme dan Arah Baru Kajian Islam di Barat*, trans., Muamirotun. Yogyakarta: Fajar Media Press. M. Arfan Mu'ammam, Abdul Wahid Hasan dkk. (2017). *Studi Islam Kontemporer, Perspektif Insider/Outsider*. Yogyakarta: Ircisod. And much more.

4. Jujun S. Suriasumantri. (2015). *Filsafat Ilmu, Sebuah Apresiasi Terhadap Ilmu, Agama, dan Seni*. Jakarta: Pustaka Sinar Harapan, 193.

5. Jujun S. Suriasumantri. (2005). *Filsafat Ilmu, Sebuah Pengantar Populer*. Jakarta: Sinar Harapan.

6. Stuart Hampshire. (1960). *The Age of Reason*. New York: Mentor Books.

7. Giorgio de Santillana. (1957). *The Age of Adventure*. New York: Mentor Books.

8. Morton White. (1960). *The Age of Analysis*. New York: Mentor Books.

9. Matters about rationalism and empiricism as sources of scientific truth can be read Bertrand Russel. (2021). *Sejarah Filsafat Barat*, trans., Sigit Jatmiko dkk. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar. See also Vergilius Ferm, ed. (2020). *Sejarah Sistem-Sistem Filsafat*, trans., Aeon Maximus Ra. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar. See also Simon Petrus Tjahjadi. (2004). *Petualangan Intelektual, Konfrontasi dengan Para Filsuf dari Zaman Yunani Hingga Zaman Modern*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Kanisius. But the debate about rationalism and empiricism among Indonesian readers is quite an interesting to be read Jujun S. Suriasumantri. (2015). *Filsafat Ilmu, Sebuah Apresiasi Terhadap Ilmu, Agama, dan Seni*. Jakarta: Pustaka Sinar Harapan.

10. Mahbub Setiawan. (2022). *Episteme Islamisasi Nusantara, Kajian Naskah Melayu Klasik Abad XIV dan XVII*. Jakarta: Postgraduate School of UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta.

11. Walter Capps. (1955). *Religious Studies: The Making of a Discipline*. Minneapolis: Forter Press.

12. This "critical" and "explorative" attitude has become a prominent characteristic since the Enlightenment era in Western Europe to modern times. On this subject see Dorinda Outram. (2019). *The Enlightenment, New Approaches to European History* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 4th printing. J. Bronowski and Bruce Mazlish. (1960). *The Western Intellectual Tradition, From Leonardo to Hegel*. New York: Barner & Noble Books.

13. Karen Armstrong. (2001). *Sejarah Tuhan*, trans. Zaimul Am. Bandung: Mizan.

14. Karen Armstrong. (2007). *The Great Transformation, Awal Sejarah Tuhan*, trans. Yuliani Liputo. Bandung: Mizan.

15. Karen Armstrong. (2001). *Berperang Demi Tuhan, Fundamentalisme dalam Islam, Kristen dan Yahudi*, trans. Satrio Wahono dkk. Jakarta: Serambi dan Mizan.

16. Karen Armstrong. (2016). *Fields of Blood, Mengurai Sejarah Hubungan Agama dan Kekerasan*, trans. Yuliani Liputo. Bandung: Mizan.

17. Karen Armstrong. (2019). *The Lost Art of Scripture, Rescuing the Sacred Texts*. London: The Bodley Head.

18. Azyumardi Azra. (2004). *Jaringan Ulama Timur Tengah dan Kepulauan Nusantara Abad XVII-XVIII*. Jakarta: Prenada Media.

19. Sartono Kartodirdjo. (2015). *Pemberontakan Petani Banten 1888*. Jakarta: Komunitas Bambu.

20. Kuntowijoyo. (2002). *Perubahan Sosial Dalam Masyarakat Agraris Madura 1850-1940*. Yogyakarta: Mata Bangsa.
21. Denys Lombard. (1996). *Nusa Jawa Silang Budaya, Vol I,II, dan III*. Jakarta: Kompas Gramedia.
22. Merle Calvin Ricklefs. (2006). *Mystic Synthesis in Java, A History of Islamization from the Fourteenth to the early Nineteenth Centuries*. Connecticut USA: EastBridge.
23. Peter Carey. (2016). *Kuasa Ramalan, Pangeran Diponegoro dan Akhir Tatanan Lama di Jawa 1785-1855 Jilid 1,2, and 3*. Jakarta, Gramedia Publisher.
24. Herry Purnomo. (2022). *Filsafat Sains, Intelektualisme, dan Riset Untuk Perubahan*. Jakarta: Kompas, 325-326.
25. His criticism of Imam Shafi'i can be read in his work, (2017). *Imam Syafi'i, Moderatisme, Eklektisme, Arabisme*. Yogyakarta: LKIS.
26. Abdurrahman Wahid. (2007). *Islam Kosmopolitan, Nilai-Nilai Indonesia dan Transformasi Kebudayaan*. Jakarta: The Wahid Institute, 25.